

Charge transfer complexes of 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-*para*-benzoquinone with drugs

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Abstract : Molecular complexes of 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-*para*-benzoquinone (DDQ) with some antibiotic drugs have been studied spectrophotometrically in chloroform. All the complexes exhibited charge transfer band(s) in the visible region where neither donor nor acceptor have any absorption. The stoichiometry of the each of the complexes is found to be 1 : 1 and is unaffected by variation of temperature. The complexes are inferred to be $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ type. The ionization potentials of the donors have been evaluated from the energies of CT bands. The stabilities and thermodynamic parameters of the complexes have been determined from the absorption studies on the CT bands. The variation of position of CT bands and the stabilities of the complexes have been correlated with the structures of the drugs.

Keywords : Charge transfer band, oscillatory strength, benzoquinone.

2,3-Dichloro-5,6-dicyano-*p*-benzoquinone (DDQ) has been shown to form complexes with a variety of organic donors, viz. aromatics, methoxy benzenes, heterocyclics, metal complexes, imidazoles, polymers etc¹. The electron affinity of DDQ reported is 1.99 eV². In continuation of our work³ it is thought worthwhile to study charge transfer complexes of DDQ with drugs like 2-methylpyrazine, albendazole, isoxsuprine, pyrimethamine, nylidrin, naproxen, nerolin, 2-amino benzonitrile 4-thiazole(2-amino- α -methoxyimino)ethyl acetate (Syn), verapamil and primaquine which are currently available in the market with a view to provide a tool for the quantitative estimation of the drugs. The results of the study are reported in this communication.

Results and discussion

When pale yellow coloured solution of DDQ is mixed with drugs characteristic colours were observed (Fig. 1). Each of the solution exhibited CT band(s) in their electronic spectra. Naproxen, nerolin, 4-thiazole(2-amino- α -methoxyimino)ethyl acetate (Syn) and verapamil exhibited two charge transfer bands while 2-methyl pyrazine, albendazole, isoxsuprine, pyrimethamine, nylidrin, primaquine and 2-amino benzonitrile exhibited only one CT band. The appearance of colour and exhibition of CT bands is attributed to the formation of the charge transfer complexes between the drugs and DDQ since these absorption bands are uncharacteristic of the individual com-

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectrum of DDQ and charge transfer spectrum of DDQ-drugs : (1) UV-Vis spectrum of DDQ, (2) charge transfer spectrum of DDQ-2-methyl pyrazine, (3) DDQ-albendazole, (4) DDQ-pyrimethamine, (5) DDQ-naproxen.

ponents. The wavelength (λ_{\max}) of CT band of all the complexes together with other spectral characteristics are

Table 1. Spectral characteristics of charge transfer complexes of DDQ with drugs

Sl. no.	Name of the drugs	λ_{\max} (nm)	I.P. (± 0.1 eV)	ϵ_{\max}	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ (cm^{-1})	f	D
1.	2-Methyl pyrazine	825	7.665	2500	4760	0.0514	3.002
2.	Albendazole	739	7.915	2300	5880	0.0584	3.029
3.	Isoxsuprine	727	7.955	2200	3920	0.0372	2.399
4.	Pyrimethamine	725	7.961	1900	3600	0.035	2.362
5.	Nylidrin	723	7.968	1800	3475	0.027	2.037
6.	Naproxen	700 (502)	8.048 (9.049)	1600	4857	0.033	2.230
7.	Nerolin	680 (495)	8.123 (9.052)	1550	4200	0.032	2.210
8.	2-Amino benzonitrile	576	8.340	1350	5344	0.031	1.950
9.	4-Thiazole(2-amino- α -methoxy imino)ethyl acetate (Syn)	575 (535)	8.350 (8.830)	1300	7451	0.041	2.260
10.	Verapamil	575 (532)	8.350 (8.825)	1100	2252	0.01	1.140
11.	Primaquine	565	8.400	1100	1335	0.0058	0.832

presented in Table 1. The appearance of CT band is attributed to the excitation of an electron from the HOMO of the donor to lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) of the acceptor. The appearance of double CT bands is attributed to the excitation of electron from ultimate and penultimate molecular orbitals of donor to the LUMO of the acceptor. Double CT bands may occur due to (a) excitation of electrons from two different levels of donor to the same vacant level of acceptor or (b) excitation of electron from HOMO of donor to two different vacant levels of acceptor. In the former type of CT complexes the energy gap between two CT bands ($E_{CT1} - E_{CT2}$) depends upon the donor where as in the latter type of complexes energy gap is independent of donor. In our study the energy gap depends upon the donor and hence the complexes are inferred to be of former type. The position of CT band (λ_{\max}) of drugs with DDQ is in the order : 2-methyl pyrazine > albendazole > isoxsuprine > pyrimethamine > nylidrin > naproxen > nerolin > 2-aminobenzonitrile > 4-thiazole(2-amino- α -methoxy-imino)ethyl acetate (Syn) > verapamil > primaquine. Wherever two CT bands occurred the higher wave length band is considered in the priority order.

From the structures of drugs (Chart 1) it becomes clear that 2-methyl pyrazine should be the best donor as it contains two nitrogen atoms in its ring. It is known that pyridine is more basic than benzene because of the presence of lone pair of electrons on nitrogen. Similarly pyrazine with two nitrogen atoms should act as better

donor than benzene or substituted benzenes (which are the basic structures of other drugs). Its CT band is at 825 nm. Albendazole containing benzimidazole ring with two nitrogens showed basicity next to pyrazine is understandable. Among the remaining drugs naproxen and nerolin which contain a naphthalene moiety should be the next members in the sequence. But (λ_{\max}) of these are lower than isoxsuprine and nylidrin. The enhanced basicity of nylidrin and isoxsuprine may be due to the presence of another benzene ring. When two benzene rings approximately lie parallel there is a possibility of interaction between them due to hyper conjugation which enhances the basicity of the donor ring.

The nerolin, naproxen followed the pyrimethamine, 2-aminobenzonitrile, 4-thiazole(2-amino- α -methoxy-imino)ethyl acetate (Syn) and verapamil followed the sequence. Primaquine with quinoline moiety surprisingly showed least basicity. This may be due to hydrogen bonding between N-H and a pair of electrons on the ring nitrogen which decreases the basicity of quinoline ring.

The energies of the inter molecular charge transfer bands are calculated from the frequencies of absorption, using the equation, $E_{CT} = h\nu_{CT}$.

The energies of CT bands of DDQ are linearly related to the ionization potentials of the donors in CHCl_3 by the equation, $h\nu_{CT} = 0.77I_D - 4.19$, where ν_{CT} is the frequency of the CT band, I_D is ionization potential of donor and ' h ' Planck's constant. The ionization potentials of the donors are calculated using this equation and are

Chart 1

reported in Table 1. The ionization potentials of donors in the present study are in the order : 2-methyl pyrazine < albendazole < isoxsuprine < pyrimethamine < nyldrin < naproxen < nerolin < 2-aminobenzonitrile < 4-thiazole(2-amino-α-methoxyimino)ethyl acetate (Syn) < verapamil < primaquine.

The stoichiometry of the complexes were determined by Job's continuous variation method using equimolar solutions ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) of DDQ and drugs, and the stoichiometry is found to be 1 : 1 in each case. The intersection points of Rose-Drago plots also indicate a 1 : 1

stoichiometry for the complexes. It has been observed that the ϵ for a given complex remains approximately constant over the temperature range studied. The constancy of ϵ may also be taken as a further evidence in support of species with 1 : 1 stoichiometry in all the drugs-DDQ complexes. Spectral characteristics of the complexes are given in Table 1.

$f = 4.319 \times 10^{-9}$. $\epsilon_{\max} \cdot \Delta v_{1/2}$ have also been calculated.

Transition dipole moment of the complex⁵, $D = 0.09582 (\epsilon_{\max} \Delta v_{1/2} / \nu_{\max})^{1/2}$ have also been computed

from the extinction coefficients and half-band widths and are reported in Table 1 together with the oscillatory strengths.

For a given complex the extinction coefficients, the oscillatory strengths and the dipole moments are also found to be almost independent of temperature. For a set of complexes of a series of chemically related donors, with a common acceptor ϵ_{\max} is expected to increase with increase in interaction between donor and acceptor i.e. decrease in ionization potentials or increase in stability constants. Consequently the f and D also expected to be in the same order as ϵ . In DDQ-drugs complexes such a relation is not observed. This may be due to contact charge transfer (CCT) transitions (collision between donor and acceptor molecules) occurring along with the simple charge transfer transitions (CT) of the complex suggested by Evans⁶ proposed that if CCT occurs the apparent extinction coefficients of the complex will be larger than that in absence of CCT. The observed ϵ value is related to ϵ_{\max} of CT and ϵ_{\max} of CCT by the equation,

$$\epsilon_{\text{obs}} = \epsilon_{\text{CT}} + \frac{\alpha \epsilon'}{K}$$

where α is number of possible contact sites for the species in excess, around any molecule of the second species, ϵ' is the extinction coefficient for the CCT process based on the potential contact concentration and K is a constant. Thus, the observed ϵ depends on the α , ϵ' and K which cannot be evaluated a priori. The values of ϵ'

are found to be of the order 10^6 , thus the second term of the equation determines the observed ϵ . Further the randomness f and D may also be due to variation of $\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ from drug to drug.

Electron releasing ability of the drug are in the order : 2-methyl pyrazine > albendazole > isoxsuprine > pyrimethamine > nylidrin > naproxen > nerolin > 2-aminobenzonitrile > 4-thiazole(2-amino- α -methoxyimino)ethyl acetate (Syn) > verapamil > primaquine (Table 2).

The K values are also found to decrease with increasing ionization potentials and a straight line was obtained when logarithmic functions of K are plotted against ionization potentials of donors with some exception because all the donors are not structurally related (there are mononuclear, binuclear aromatics and heterocyclics) (Fig. 2).

The thermodynamic parameters viz. ΔH and ΔS were evaluated from the variation of stability constants with temperature using vant Hoff's method. A plot of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ gave straight line, from the slope and intercept of which the ΔH , ΔS have been evaluated. The ΔG at 25 °C were calculated using the equation,

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \text{ and are presented in Table 2.}$$

A linear relationship is obtained between ΔH and ΔS for all CT complexes. It is interesting to note that the sterically unhindered complex formation indicates that the interactions is of the π - π^* type.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of CT complexes of DDQ with drugs

Sl. no.	Name of the drug	K values at various temperatures					$-\Delta H$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S$ (cal deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)
		K_{10} °C	K_{15} °C	K_{20} °C	K_{25} °C	K_{30} °C			
1.	2-Methyl pyrazine	143.722	97.414	66.905	46.535	32.757	12.6	34.65	2.275
2.	Albendazole	133.494	91.039	62.902	44.001	31.149	12.4	34.091	2.241
3.	Isoxsuprine	127.368	87.130	60.381	42.362	30.070	12.30	33.839	2.241
4.	Pyrimethamine	75.30	52.66	37.26	26.67	19.31	11.6	32.40	1.94
5.	Nylidrin	67.40	48.02	34.6	26.20	18.50	11.00	30.50	1.911
6.	Naproxen	47.10	34.00	24.70	18.20	13.80	10.6	29.80	1.72
7.	Nerolin	43.00	31.4	23.10	17.20	13.00	10.21	28.60	1.69
8.	2-Amino benzonitrile	27.9	20.8	15.80	12.00	9.26	9.4	26.60	1.47
9.	4-Thiazole(2-amino- α -methoxyimino)ethyl acetate (Syn)	22.00	16.60	12.70	9.8	7.658	9.01	25.7	1.34
10.	Verapamil	15.881	12.04	9.310	7.225	5.645	8.8	25.607	1.169
11.	Primaquine	15.306	11.701	9.027	7.026	5.513	8.7	25.327	1.152

Fig. 2. A plot of $\log K$ vs I_p of donors (donor numbers as in Table 1).

Experimental

Materials :

DDQ : The commercial sample of DDQ obtained from Aldrich was recrystallised from benzene-chloroform (2 : 3) mixture and its purity was checked by TLC (m.p. 213–214 °C). Chloroform spectrograde solvent was used without any further purification. Drugs procured from pharmaceutical laboratories – Dr. Reddy Labs and Hetero Drugs (Pvt) Ltd., Hyderabad and were purified by recrystallisation. Drugs were also procured from various bulk drug manufacturers.

Methods : The UV-Vis spectra of the individual components and the charge transfer complexes were recorded on Shimadzu 140 UV-Vis doublebeam spectrophotometer using a matched pair of quartz cells of 10 mm path length. The optical density data was collected at λ_{\max} of CT band on Shimadzu 240. These instruments are fitted with thermostated sample compartment with digital temperature display. The temperatures above 25 °C were attained by electrical heating of the sample compartment while the lower temperatures by circulating cold water around the cuvettes. The concentration of DDQ = 1.0×10^{-3} – 1.5×10^{-3} M and the concentrations of drugs are

in the range of 0.001–0.044 M. The solution concentration was set such that it produced the complex with optical density between 0.2–1.8. The absorption band, due to acceptor or donor individually have fallen to the base line much before the wavelength of CT absorption. However, the lower wavelength side of the CT bands is complicated by other absorption, probably due to the complexed donor. The complicated CT bands were analysed by using the relation put forward earlier,

$$v_h - v_l / 2(v_m - v_l) = 1.2$$

where v_m is frequency at peak maximum, v_l and v_h are frequencies of lower and higher side of the peak at half band width. The formation constants of the complexes were determined by Rose-Drago method⁷,

$$K^{-1} = d/\epsilon - ([D_0] + [A_0]) + [D_0][A_0]\epsilon/d$$

where d is the absorbance and ϵ is the molar extinction coefficient of the complex. The composition of the complexes was determined by Job's continuous variation method. Thermodynamic parameters ΔH and ΔS were determined from the plots of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ using Vant Hoff's equation.

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References

1. Rahman Zaffsur and Nasal Hoda, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2003, **31**, 381; Moustafa and A. M. Azza, *Bell. Fac. Pharm.*, 1999, **37**, 9; P. C. Dwivedi and Rama Agarwal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 366; H. S. Randhawa, R. Sachdeva and A. Singla, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1986, **31**, 675.
2. Y. Lida, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, **44**, 1430.
3. T. Vinod Kumar, T. Veeraiah and G. Venkateswarlu, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 2000, **112**, 119; T. Vinod Kumar, T. Charan Singh and G. Venkateswarlu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 622; T. Vinod Kumar, T. Veeraiah and G. Venkateswarlu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 466.
4. A. Ashrafa-Alay, A. Alla Hassan S, Yousef, Mahmmmed, About-Fetouch, Mourad and Henning Hopf, *Monatshette fir Chemie*, 1992, **123**, 179.
5. H. Tsubomura and R. Lang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2085.
6. D. F. Evans, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4229.
7. N. J. Rose and R. S. Drago, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 6138.